

The Colorful Effects of Positive Reinforcement to the Learning of Kindergarten Learners: The Journey of a Kindergarten Teacher

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Abstract. This study aimed to describe the colorful experiences of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcement to kindergarten learners. The participants were the ten kindergarten teachers in Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan Cotabato, utilizing phenomenological design to explore their colorful experiences. A semi-structured interview guide was used to gather the data. Ethical considerations were observed in data collection. The themes were extracted using thematic content analysis. The findings were: diversity of learners' needs, behavioral management, transition periods, and development of core values are the experiences of kindergarten teachers; their coping mechanisms with the challenges encountered are consistency in application, use of verbal praise, use of complimenting gesture, enforce reward system, impose individualized reinforcement, celebrate small success, and employ reflective practice; and individualization and specification is key, emphasis on intrinsic motivation, heighten flexibility and adaptability, establish positive classroom culture, and adopt holistic teaching approach are the educational management insights. The recommendation advanced included creating and communicating clear regulations by the Department of Education that encourage the use of positive reinforcement practices in early childhood education. Ensure that policies are consistent with best practices and provide a framework for their implementation across schools.

KEY WORDS

1. Colorful experiences
2. coping mechanisms
3. educational management insights
4. kindergarten teachers

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1. Introduction

When a kindergartener goes to school, they face a new environment in which they are unfamiliar and confused. It is an environment that they have just stepped into for the first time in their lives. This is also the environment where they are open to learning, and a learner opens their minds more when they receive positive reinforcements for the efforts that they push through in their activities. Usually, when a kid or a learner, in general, receives a suitable remark for their work, their mind would be conditioned to stay consistent so as to receive the same compliment or an even better one in the future. This, then, points out that positive reinforcement brings out colors from the mind of a kindergarten—which is an excellent way to

push in as a technique for educational management. According to Costa (2021), which was cited in their article by O'Connor and McCartney (2007), giving a kindergartener something to look forward to each time they respond appropriately is known as positive reinforcement, and the goal is to encourage this behavior. Students who receive this kind of feedback are more motivated to keep their conduct since it improves their behavior and makes them feel inspired and engaged in their current activity. It was also mentioned that just as children deserve to be told about their performance in their daily sessions, it is crucial to let children know the results of each session or the remarks. From this perspective, this is one way of helping kindergarteners evaluate their work better and understand what to improve and what to keep consistently. It was also mentioned in the study of Rumfola (2017), in which they cited what Downing (n.d.) stated that for both kindergarteners and teachers in the educational system, a teacher's capacity to mold proper classroom conduct while putting out misbehavior is essential to the learning environment. Strategies that increase and shape positive behaviors, which are positive reinforcements, are more successful than those that penalize in any learning setting. This tells us that positive reinforcements are indeed what pushes learners to be more open to the disciplinary actions that teachers may introduce to them whenever they do an activity that may not be likely. In a study by Bulacan DepEd (2015), positive and constructive discipline is effective. It entails establishing learning objectives and coming up with positive responses to difficult circumstances. Schools should respect children's developmental stages, their rights to bodily integrity and dignity, and their right to engage in their education actively. This pushes the education motion to positively criticize and remark on the students' efforts, since as kids who are still using their creative juices and growing intellects, they need the validation that they crave to know whether they are on the right track or not. Positive reinforcement is indeed helpful as a form of disciplinary motion as well since it pushes kindergarteners on a positive note. For example, they make a mistake, but they don't feel fear of making it. They learn positively that it is wrong. This helps them grow and can also be applied in their educational learning. As mentioned by Bright Wheel (2023), using positive reinforcement is a crucial tactic for controlling kindergarteners' behavior. Giving a reward after a desired behavior has been shown encourages the repeating of that behavior. Children can either strengthen or learn new behavior thanks to these incentives. According to research, implementing various forms of positive reinforcement improves desired behavior while also aiding in teaching young children. Positive reinforcement is not bribery, despite what you might believe. In terms of education, there are indeed effects of positive reinforcement – repeating the motion of behavior that was being praised can shout consistency in the long run and may shape the kindergartener as they grow and learn better the different academic branches. As stated by Hamm (2018), positive reinforcement is a style of behavior management used in education that emphasizes rewarding positive student conduct. It differs from positive punishment in that it places more emphasis on praising pupils for their good deeds than it does on correcting misconduct. For instance, you could verbally commend a kid who is appropriately putting away their marker bin if another student is not doing so. This will encourage other students to strive for excellent behavior and will reinforce the behavior you wish to see. Through this definition, one was opened to the view that positive reinforcement can promote or motivate one to continue doing well in academics, which adds to disciplinary measures. A kindergartener exposed to this is molded to become a better learner as they increase level per level. This type of measure being exposed

as early as kindergarten is a great start of character development, which greatly influences academic performance or even social performance. In the local scenario, the kindergarten learners have found themselves in a position where they are open to learning new environments in the aspect of education. These learners have responded positively into having a better performance through the praises that they gather and indebted in their mind as they continuously put efforts in their tasks. As the learning takes place in the new normal, the researcher observed that there were several challenges in teaching the kindergarten pupils especially in adding the con-

cept of positive reinforcement. It is quite evident that some kindergarteners would be used to the reinforcement that sometimes they would be too comfortable and lose track in the educational performance. We used the different positive reinforcement techniques to encourage the learners to pursue their boost in academic performance while at home or even in school grounds. As a researcher, this study was proposed to find out how far did the kindergarten teachers employed the different positive reinforcement techniques in educational settings to kindergarteners.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to unleash the experiences of the kindergarten teachers in teaching kindergarteners with the applied technique of positive reinforcements as means to improve performance in education and mold their personality as they grow academically. The challenges of the kindergarten teachers as well as their insights shall be determined at the end of this study particularly in Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan Cotabato.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aimed to describe the experiences of kindergarten teachers in Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan Cotabato in applying positive reinforcement to the kindergarten learners during the School Year 2023-2024. Further, this study explored the following questions:

- (1) What are the colorful experiences of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcements to kindergarteners?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of kindergarten teachers as they apply positive reinforcement to the efforts of kindergarteners?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of kindergarten teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Positive Reinforcements. It is the act of reinforcing positive criticisms and remarks to learners that exert effort or show an exemplary output for a particular task. It is the manner of giving validation in a way that a learner's output and effort have been recognized and appreciated. Colorful Effects. It is the creative way of explaining how the effects

of positive reinforcement bring out bright diversities in a student's learning and make them explore new environments and dimensions to receive remarks and criticisms that are likely and heart-felt to them as they achieve goals with desirability. Lived Experiences. It is the actions and views where the teacher has first-hand experience on their journey as kindergarten teachers. It was their experience on positive reinforcements with kindergarteners that were shared, which they have the first perspective on.

1.4. Significant of the Study—

To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Personnel. The DepEd, particularly the District of, Arakan West. to look into the implementation and promotion of the positive reinforcements to the progress of performance in the academical field. This study shall provide information on the clarity of the kindergarten teachers activities as they apply positive reinforcement techniques. The School Principals and Head Teachers. For the school principals and school heads to gain a clear understanding and interpretation of the

promotion of positive reinforcements, as well as its benefits and changes brought to the grade statistics and performances of kindergarteners. The Kindergarten Teachers. The findings of the study shall provide the scenario as to how the positive reinforcement, specifically positive criticisms and remarks, as forwarded to parents were used and assisted the kindergarten pupils learn how to consistently perform better in academics. The Future Researchers. For the future researchers to take into consideration some other aspects of kindergarten learning and may duplicate this study in another area or location.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is anchored on the theory of Operant Conditioning Theory by Skinner in 1953, which explains that the behavior of a person is influenced by its consequences, whether good or bad. It is shaped according to what they hear or the feedback that they receive. It is meant that after hearing the feedback, they are to be influenced by using the feedback as information that would guide their subsequent behavior or action. An example of this would be the concept of positive reinforcement, where the behavior of a kindergartener is greatly influenced by the consequences that they receive or hear. If they receive a positive remark, they usually get affected by that remark, and they shape their following behavior by either improving what they have done well, doing it consistently for the next days, or even last as they grow older. The theory of Operant Conditioning helps us understand the concept of how minds may be molded and conditioned to strive for better performances, especially in terms of academics. However, the theory revolves around more than just positive reinforcement. In viewing the Operant Conditioning Theory from a bigger or wider perspective, the theory mostly covers positive reinforcement, as well as negative reinforcement, and the least

suggested which is punishment. All of these factors contribute to a change or an influence in character, most especially in a kindergartener's behavior after showcasing an action and receiving a consequence about it, whether positive or negative. According to McLeod (2023), there are three types of critical points of the theory in Operant Conditioning. One of which is the main anchor of the study, which is the concept of positive reinforcement. It is mentioned in the article that positive reinforcement includes having an increase in the frequency of a behavior when applied. An example cited in the article was that when you finish your homework early, you get to watch the movies as a reward. This stimulates the action of doing it frequently to be able to receive more desirable rewards. In relation to the study, a kindergartener being told that they are to be given a star stamp, for example, after showing exemplary or outstanding work, is an example of positive reinforcement and will most likely spark consistency in the work of the kindergartener, or may even improve in hopes to get a bigger reward or compliment. It was also mentioned in McLeod's (2023) article that although not anchored to this study, negative reinforcement is also one of the types of Operant Conditioning in Skinner's theory. It was

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

mentioned that when negative reinforcement is present or is being done, it is said to stimulate a decrease in activity or lesser activity from the behavior they have shown. For example, when one has made a mistake, and when negative reinforcement is applied or evident in the situation, one is most likely to avoid doing the same behavior again – which connects to the decrease of behavior as an influence to the consequence of what they have heard as a feedback to the behavior they have shown first. Here, we can justify that, indeed, the Operant Conditioning

Theory of Skinner (1953) thoroughly anchors the study as students, most especially focused on kindergarteners, are growing students – students who are still being molded. When exposed to a positive environment where they are able to grow and foster their minds with positive reinforcements from teachers or guardians or even fellow classmates, they are able to stimulate better behavior to be conducted or consistently done, which also molds them to become people who perform better both academically and non-academically.

2. Methodology

This chapter examined the Philosophical Assumptions, which discussed the papers' assumptions, and the qualitative assumptions, and explained the research paradigm. The paper thoroughly covered the Design and Procedure, Participants of this Research, as well as the Data Collection technique and how the data were processed. It should be underlined that Ethical Considerations were thoroughly recorded and followed. Finally, the Researcher's Role was explored in this chapter. Focus groups, in-depth interviews, and participant observation are the three most popular qualitative research techniques. Each approach is best suited for gathering a certain kind of data. For gathering information on normally occurring activities in their typical settings, participant observation is acceptable. The best method for gathering information about people's backgrounds, viewpoints, and experiences is through in-depth interviews (IDI), especially when delicate subjects are being discussed. Focus groups are useful for gathering information on a group's cultural norms and for creating comprehensive overviews of subjects that are important to the represented

cultural groups or subgroups. The researcher made sound recordings of the interviews and group discussions, which the researcher then transcribed and evaluated. Individual interviews with teachers were the major focus of the study since the researcher wanted to learn directly about the participants' experiences, thoughts, sentiments, and situations when teaching primary pupils with positive reinforcement.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework for gathering, analyzing, and interpreting facts in a certain field of research. It creates the context for the upcoming findings and judgments. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. The various forms of typical philosophical assumptions are discussed here. Stanage (1987) links the term "paradigm" back to its Greek and Latin roots, where it means "pattern, model, among examples, an exemplar or model to follow in which design actions are taken." A paradigm, in other words, is an activity of surrendering to a point of view. According to Payne (2005), the paradigm takes into account the fact that each person has unique experiences and hence bases their perception of reality on these experiences. Reality is regarded as a relative construct, yet shared social constructs can contribute to a group or society's perception of reality. In the current study, the above strategy was followed, which resulted in the formulation of particular research questions outlined in Chapter One. These questions were based on an awareness of the research in this subject and aimed to expand on existing knowledge while allowing for new information about the current process to come forth from individuals' experiences within it. Ontology. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multifaceted, as observed by research participants. For the qualitative researcher, the ontological question tackles the nature of reality. Individuals participating in the research scenario build reality. Thus, there are numerous realists, such as the researchers, the persons being researched, and the reader or audience understanding the study. The experiences of kindergarten instructors on the learner's letter recognition with the use of audio-video approaches were pulled forth in this study. In this study, I relied on the participants' voices and interpretations through substantial quotations, themes that mirrored their words, and evidence of varied viewpoints. The study participants' replies were categorized and evaluated in order to create and develop the universality and confidentiality of responses. I made certain that the participants' replies were appropriately coded to ensure the trustworthiness of the results. The researcher maintained the truthfulness of the replies and avoided developing personal biases as the investigation progressed. Epistemology. According to Guba and Lincoln (1985), as referenced by Creswell (2013), the researcher aimed to reduce the gap between himself or herself and the participants based on epistemological assumptions. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011), he proposes that as a researcher, he or she communicates, invests moments in the field with respondents, and becomes an "insider." Different researchers "hold explicit belief" in this regard. The goal of this study is to compile information regarding kindergarten teachers' experiences with adding positive reinforcement to their way of teaching, or if they have already added the concept of positive reinforcement, their observations on the kindergarten are to be noted. Axiology. According to Creswell (2013), the function of values in a study is crucial. According to axiology, the researcher should freely disclose the values that create the story and include their own perspective as well as the interpretation of the participants. The researcher respected and cher-

ished every bit of information acquired from participants. The researcher recognized the personal and valuable character of the study's findings. As a result, the researcher kept the participant's responses and carefully analyzed them in light of the participant's personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical premise emphasized that the researcher may write in a

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experience of the kindergarten teachers as they used the addition of positive reinforcement to student or kindergartener learning to improve the learning and academic performance of the learners were explored in various schools in Arakan West District, Dorooluman Arakan Cotabato. The researcher's interest in kindergarten teachers' experiences became the basis for conducting qualitative research, which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited by Gerodias (2013), considered useful in searching for "meanings and motivations

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—The qualitative research method of phenomenology was applied in this study. A number of teachers who have firsthand knowledge of an event, circumstance, or experience were interviewed. The data was then examined and reread for similar words and themes, which were subsequently aggregated to generate meaning clusters (Creswell,

2.4. *Research Participants*—The participants in this study were composed of ten (10) informants. The selected informants were the kindergarten teachers from various DepEd schools in Arakan West District, Dorooluman

literary, informal manner with a personal voice, utilizing qualitative terminology and limited definition. In the framework of the study, the researcher utilized the first person to describe the experiences of kindergarten instructors in implicating the use of positive reinforcement to kindergarteners and its effects on their learning and performance.

that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." This need was supposed to be met by bringing the tales of the kindergarten instructors in such a way that, as David (2005) said, the themes, symbolism, and significance of the experiences would be portrayed. Two assumptions underpin phenomenological inquiry. The first is that experience is a legitimate, rich, and satisfying source of information. The researcher hoped that by using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the personal experiences and perspectives of the kindergarten teachers on positive reinforcement and its effects on the learning and performance improvements of the kindergarteners, as well as their insights, would be highlighted.

2013). The researcher arrived at a more thorough knowledge of the phenomena by constructing the universal meaning of the event, circumstance, or experiences. In this study, phenomenology aims to extract the most pure, unaltered data, and in some interpretations, the researcher uses bracketing to chronicle personal interactions with the subject in order to help separate himself or herself from the process.

Arakan Cotabato. All the participants of this study were the kindergarten teachers who had the experience in teaching with positive reinforcement in different academic activities to support their learners' learning. These teach-

ers must have at least 3-5 years' experience in teaching kindergarten pupils. In general, qualitative studies need a lower sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative research samples should be big enough to elicit input on the majority, if not all, of the impressions. Acquiring either all or most of the experiences will result in saturation. When introducing additional respondents to a research fails to bring in more viewpoints or information, the study is said to be saturated. For reaching an accept-

able sample size in qualitative research, Glaser and Strauss (1967) advocate the idea of saturation. Creswell (1998) proposes five (5) to 25 phenomenological investigations, whereas Morse (1994) supports at least six (6). When it comes to choosing an acceptable sample size in qualitative research, there are no hard and fast guidelines. The time provided, resources readily accessible, and study objectives can all help decide qualitative sample size (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Given the nature of qualitative research, interactions between researchers and participants can be ethically hard for the former because they are directly involved in various stages of the study. As a result, developing particular ethical norms in this regard is critical. The relationship and intimacy established between researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a variety of moral concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as consideration for anonymity, the establishment of open and truthful communication, and the avoidance of inaccuracies. According to Richards and Schwartz (2002), a core ethical necessity of all research is that it be scientifically reliable. The study must be well-planned and executed by qualified researchers with appropriate levels of experience and monitoring. It should be worthwhile in the sense that the end outcome produces. Furthermore, Sanjari (2014) stated that informed consent has been regarded as a vital aspect of ethical considerations in research conducted in several domains. It is critical for qualitative researchers to establish prior to collecting which pieces of information will be gathered and how they will be used. The individual also mentioned that for any research involving identifiable subjects, obtaining informed con-

sent is a necessary requirement. However, there may be instances where an ethics committee determines that obtaining such consent is not feasible, and the benefits of the research outweigh the potential risks of harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study is that participants provide written consent after being informed, both through speech as well as in written form, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions that are probable to be collected, the dissemination to which the results will be put, the method of confidentiality, and the extent to which participants' statements will be used in reports. Participants ought to have time to think about their involvement and to ask the researcher questions. In this study, the researcher considered ethical issues as part of the qualitative research procedure. It was the researcher's obligation to fully tell those who participated about the various parts of the investigation in understandable language. The following concerns require clarification, which are the nature of the study, the possible involvement of the participants, the identity of the person conducting the study, the goal of the study, and how the findings will be publicized and used. Similarly, this work will be submitted to the Rizal Memorial College, graduate school's ethics committee for verification and clearance.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—

The researcher's job in this research was to try and understand the study participants' thoughts and feelings. It entails getting informants to discuss topics that are highly personal to them. Sometimes, the events being studied are vivid in the participant's consciousness, while other times it may be difficult to relive old

2.7. *Data Collection*—In the words of Creswell (2013), finding individuals or locations to research, as well as gaining access to and establishing rapport with participants, is a key element in the process. Establishing a technique for deliberate sampling of persons or venues is a closely connected phase in the process. After the inquirer has chosen the venues or persons, judgments must be made about the best data-gathering methods. To get the details, the researcher creates protocols or written procedures for data collection, such as conversational or observational procedures. In addition, the researcher must anticipate data collecting concerns, known as "field issues," that may arise, such as insufficient data, the need to depart the field or site erratically, or leading to lost information. Lastly, the qualitative researcher has to decide how to keep data so that it is conveniently accessible and safeguarded from harm or loss. The data gathering procedure in this study consists of seven parts. The first is the location or person; the participants were kindergarten teachers from Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan Cotabato. The second step is access and rapport; an authorization letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate stu-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all data obtained was thoroughly scrutinized and analyzed. The researcher began by sharing their own encounters with the phenomena under investigation. The researcher began by detailing

experiences. The researcher's primary job is to protect participants and their data, regardless of how the data is gathered. Mechanisms for such protection must be properly communicated to participants and authorized by a competent research ethical review board prior to the start of the research.

dent for division superintendent approval; a letter of permission was prepared for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the involved elementary teachers for easy data collection. The third method is purposeful sampling, which requires that all participants have observed the incident under examination. Ten (10) participants were recruited for this investigation. Experienced kindergarten teachers were chosen as the group of persons who could best inform the researcher about the research topic. They were also identified as witnesses to the incident who may assist with data collection. The fourth category is data types; the method of gathering information, which was principally engaged in the In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the ten (10) informants. The fifth aspect is the recording processes; in the process of observation and interviewing procedures, a procedure was employed. A pre-designed form for recording data gathered during an observation or interview. The sixth concern was field difficulties; this study used restricted data collecting. The seventh and last phase was data storage; Davidson (1996) proposed the use of databases in backing up material acquired and track changes for all sorts of research investigations.

her own encounter with the phenomena. This is a means to separate the researcher's own experiences from the participants' experiences. She compiled a collection of important remarks. She then seeks comments indicating how indi-

viduals were perceiving the issue, ranks these major statements in order of importance, and tries to create a compilation of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping remarks. The researcher gathered the key statements and organized them into bigger information units known as "meaning units" or themes. She produced a summary of "what" the study's subjects experienced with the phenomena. She then produced a description of "how" the incident occurred. This is known as "structural description," and the inquirer considers the environment and setting in which the phenomena was observed. Finally, she developed a synthesis of the textual and structural descriptions of the phenomena. This section illustrates the "core" of what happened and the culmination of phenomenological research. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis attempts to find recurring themes in interview data. One of the benefits of thematic analysis is the fact that it is a versatile method that can be used for both exploratory studies, where the person conducting the study has no idea what patterns are being sought, and more deductive research, where the researcher knows exactly what he or she is looking for. Whatever form of study is conducted and for what goal, the most essential aspect of the analysis is to ensure the researcher honors the data and attempts to portray the interview findings as accurately as they can (Montensen, 2020). Document Analysis. Document analysis is a type of qualitative research in which documentary material is analyzed using a systematic approach to

answer particular research questions. Document analysis, like other qualitative research methodologies, necessitates frequent inspection, study, and decoding of the results in order to obtain significance and factual understanding of the construct being examined. Document analysis can be performed as standalone research or as part of a broader qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is frequently used to triangulate findings from other data sources (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). Triangulation of Data. Using many methods to collect information regarding the same issue is referred to as triangulation. This is a means of ensuring the reliability of research by using a range of approaches to gather data on the same issue, which includes diverse sorts of samples as well as data collection methodologies. However, the goal of triangulation is to capture distinct aspects of the same phenomena rather than to cross-validate data (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. Environmental triangulation is only used in investigations when the findings may be impacted by environmental conditions. This sort of triangulation makes use of many settings, locations, and other characteristics such as time, day, and season of the investigation. The goal is to establish which of these elements influences the information received, and then adjust those factors to see if the results are the same. In this study, such triangulation was adopted since, as previously stated, the use of environmental triangulation best suited the environment of the research being undertaken.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—Based on Braun and Clark (2006), there are two types of qualitative data analysis approaches. The first category includes methods that are driven by an epistemological or theoretical position and have limiting variation in how they are utilized within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomeno-

logical analysis (IPA), as well as methods that are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can thus be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA), and narrative analysis (NA). The second category covers strategies that are independent of theory and epistemology and may thus be employed across

a wide variety of theoretical and epistemological approaches. Thematic analysis is one such approach that, due to its theoretical flexibility, "provides a flexible and useful instrument for study that can conceivably offer a comprehensive and thorough, yet complex account of data" (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Several processes in theme analysis were seen by me. Transcription was the initial step in collecting qualitative data for evaluation from tape recordings. This was carried out to obtain a better understanding of the data and gain a better understanding of it. I did the transcription with a desktop computer and an excellent speaker, using my own resources. I listened to the interviews over multiple nights to have a better understanding of the intricacies of the participants' language and semantics. In terms of deciding on norms with transcribers, practice differed greatly. Some academics, such as those interested in comprehensive transcriptions for dialogues or narrative analysis, negotiated their way into the needed layout and standards. Others were occasionally less actively involved and accepted the conventions often utilized by the person transcribing the material. The following stage is data extraction and analysis. While listening to the recordings, I employed manual procedures such as note keeping and summarizing. My manual approach often includes verbatim recordings of chosen spoken utterances. I chose quotations concerning major topics or when what was stated sounded significant or fascinating. My thesis adviser taught me a variety of strategies, which I applied. I used colored markers to

mark up transcripts and cut and paste data. I employed the framework approach developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003) in the form of theme grids and charts. This strategy came in handy as I was coding, organizing, and gathering data for questioning. This method was really helpful in recognizing the connections and linkages between situations. All of these efforts and procedures included preserving exact spoken words from transcripts so that they could be cross-referenced to themed displays or maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I became acquainted with the data by reading the entire set and jotting down early thoughts. Phase 2. I created the first codes, with coded being the most basic pieces of raw data that can identify an intriguing aspect of the data. Phase 3. I looked for topics by categorizing different codes into prospective themes and compiling all data extracted inside those themes. Phase 4. I went through the themes and polished them deeper (at the scale of coded data extracts and the complete data set), creating a thematic map that depicted links between themes and sub-themes. Phase 5. I created and labeled topics to ensure that the reader gets a basic understanding of what the subject is about. Phase 6. I created the report to persuade the reader of the analysis's worth and validity (both within and across themes), and I used data excerpts integrated inside an analytic narrative to present points about the research issue.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and reliability are all aspects of trustworthiness. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is highly crucial since the conclusion and finding of the research study will depend on the method of how it is being done by the researcher. The

credibility of a research study is critical in determining its worth. Because of the nature of qualitative research, all data and information must be honest. The researcher's study is good for one to comprehend, share, and be satisfied of since it is trustworthy. Credibility refers to the qualitative researcher's belief in the validity

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

of the research study’s results. The researcher in this study thought that being honest in all you do is vital for achieving meaningful achievement. The researcher has no negative records or administrative concerns that jeopardize her reputation. Transferability The qualitative researcher exhibits transferability by demonstrating that the research study’s findings are relevant to different situations. In this example, "other contexts" might refer to similar conditions, populations, and events. The consequences of employing a graphic organizer as a tool in teaching reading comprehension have already been explored by the researcher. In the realms of analysis and creation, the employment of graphic organizers as a tool in teaching reading comprehension is beneficial. The researcher is interested in learning about the students’ perspectives on applying this method. Confirmability . The degree of neutrality in the research study’s conclusions is referred to as confirmability. In other words, the conclusions are based on the replies of the

participants rather than any potential bias or personal objectives of the researcher. This includes ensuring that researcher bias does not affect the understanding of what study participants stated in order to suit a specific narrative. In this case, the researcher meticulously records the information utilizing the audit trail, highlighting each stage of data analysis that was performed in order to offer an explanation for the conclusions taken. This helps to show that the conclusions of the research study appropriately depict the reactions of the participants. Dependability. is the degree to which the study could be replicated by other researchers and the results would be consistent. In other words, if someone wants to repeat your study, they should be able to do so using the information in your research report and receive equivalent results. In order to prove dependability, a qualitative researcher might utilize inquiry audit, which requires an independent person to verify and examine the research method and data analysis to guarantee

that the findings are consistent and repeatable. The usage of a database in this component is critical for storing up information collected and tracking changes for all sorts of research investigations. All data gathered must be appropriately stored for future reference. According to Gasson (2004), dependability addresses the fundamental issue that "the manner in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the findings and discussion based on the data gathered. The presentation is organized in four sections: first, the colorful experiences of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcements to kindergarteners; second, the coping mechanisms of kindergarten teachers as they apply positive reinforcement to the efforts of kindergarteners; third, the educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of kindergarten teachers; and fourth, the synthesis of the findings.

3.1. Colorful Experiences of Kindergarten Teachers in Applying Techniques in Positive Reinforcements to Kindergarteners—Presented in Figure 3 is the four (4) colorful experiences of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcements to kindergarteners. The colorful experiences include the following: (1) diversity of learners' needs, (2) behavioral management, (3) transition periods, and (4) development of core values.

3.1.1. Diversity of Learners' Needs—It shows that one of the experiences of Kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcement to kindergartens is having diversity of learners' needs. According to the participants, kindergarteners come from diverse backgrounds with different needs, learning styles, and preferences. A single approach to positive reinforcement may not be effective for all students. They experienced identifying and catering to the individual needs of each child. This finding is supported by the claim of Gwen (2019) that positive reinforcement is a powerful tool for motivating and encouraging learners, but the diversity of learners' needs means that what constitutes positive reinforcement can vary widely among individuals. While Williams (2021) pointed out that distinct learners have different learning preferences and styles. Some learners learn best through images and diagrams, while others learn best through aural methods or hands-on experiences. Recognizing and adjusting to these variances can improve the learning process. Learners are motivated by a variety of causes. Some of them are innately motivated, while others may need outside incentive. Teachers may create interesting and meaningful learning experiences by understanding what motivates individual pupils. With this, teachers are advise to involve children in deciding what constitutes positive reinforcement for them. Allow them to express their choices and give them the opportunity to create their own goals. This fosters a sense of independence and ownership in their learning (Morin, 2022).

3.1.2. Behavioral Management—The participants reveal that one of the experiences they encountered is managing misbehaviors of kindergartens. Some learners exhibit challenging behaviors that are not easily addressed through traditional positive reinforcement. According to them, they need to employ additional strategies, such as individualized behavior plans

or collaboration with support staff, to address more complex behavioral issues. Parallel to this finding, Costa (2021) pointed out that positive reinforcement behavioral management entails utilizing ways to enhance positive behaviors while decreasing or addressing difficult behaviors. When children demonstrate desired behaviors, teachers must reinforce them with praise, awards, or other forms of positive reinforcement. Positive reinforcement can encourage kids to maintain those behaviors. Moreover, when rewarding positive behaviors, teachers must provide immediate and detailed feedback. They

3.1.3. Transition Periods—Learners at this age is transitioning their habits from home to school. Thus, teachers need to inculcate to mind of the learners the sense of responsiveness. According to them, transition periods, such as arrival, departure, and transitions between activities, can be challenging for maintaining positive behavior. They find it difficult to provide timely reinforcement during these transitions, leading to disruptions or inconsistent application of positive reinforcement. Craig (2019) argued that teachers may face difficulties during transition periods in kindergarten, such as switching from one activity to another or transitioning from playtime to a structured learning activity. good reinforcement throughout these transition phases necessitates careful planning to create a seamless and good experience for young learners. Kindergartens have short attention spans, and transitions can be difficult owing to a sudden shift in focus. During transition times, they may exhibit high levels of activity, making it challenging to maintain a calm and orderly transition. Some children may struggle to follow directions, causing disruptions or delays, and others differ in their amount of comfort. While some children adjust quickly, others may find shifts upsetting or confusing (Montensen, 2020). With this, Eremie and Doueyi-Fiderikumo (2018) suggest that visual cues such

have to communicate clearly what the learner performed well and link the positive reward to the observed behavior. Reinforcement is more effective when it is given at the right time. Chan (2023) suggests that teachers can establish a supportive and encouraging learning environment that fosters positive behaviors while addressing any issues that may occur by incorporating positive reinforcement into behavioral management tactics. These approaches are successful because of consistency, individualization, and a focus on teaching and modeling.

as timers, visual schedules, or countdowns can assist children understand the timing of transitions. This sends a clear message and prepares them for the impending shift. Moreover, they recommend to establish consistent transition routines. Predictability is important to children, so having a fixed schedule can help them anticipate and prepare for changes. On the other hand, Cherry (2023) claimed that positive actions must be reinforced during transitions. Children who transition smoothly, follow directions, or exhibit positive behavior during the process should be praised and rewarded. This encourages children to repeat those habits.

3.1.4. Development of Core Values—The last colorful experience of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcements to kindergarteners is, they developed and instilled the core values among learners. According to them, Kindergarten education is critical in laying the groundwork for the formation of essential values, as well as developing the character and moral direction of young learners. The finding is similar to the claim of Brightwheel (2023) that instilling core values in children is an important part of their overall development. Teachers can purposefully promote and reinforce specific core values in the classroom to help influence students' character and behavior while using positive reinforcement.

Fig. 3. Colorful Experiences of Kindergarten Teachers in Applying Techniques in Positive Reinforcements to Kindergarteners

To do this, teachers must begin by identifying the core values that they want their students to have. Respect, responsibility, kindness, honesty, perseverance, and empathy are all common values. Teachers can infuse the chosen core values into the overall culture of the classroom. These values must be discussed and modeled on a regular basis in order to become ingrained in daily interactions and activities. Each core value should connect explicitly to particular beneficial activities. For example, if the core value is "respect," behaviors such as attentive listen-

ing, polite language can be discussed, and acknowledging the opinions of others (Ackerman, 2023). With this, Winfield (2023) concluded that teachers can make a substantial contribution to their students' character development and overall well-being by actively incorporating fundamental values into the positive reinforcement framework. Positive reinforcement, when used consistently, reinforces the link between positive behaviors and the values that contribute to a positive and helpful learning environment.

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms of Kindergarten Teachers as They Apply Positive Reinforcement to the Efforts of Kindergarteners*—Presented in Figure 4 is the seven (7) coping mechanisms of Kindergarten teachers as they apply positive reinforcement to the efforts of Kindergarteners.

The coping mechanisms include the following: (1) consistency in application, (2) use of verbal praise, (3) use of complimenting gesture, (4) enforce reward system, (5) imposed individualized reinforcement, (6) celebrate small success, and (7) employ reflective practice.

3.2.1. *Consistency in Application*—One of the coping mechanisms of Kindergarten teachers as they apply positive reinforcement to the efforts of Kindergarteners is being consistent in whatever reinforcement they applied to the learners. According to them, positive reinforce-

ment must be used consistently. They make an effort to be consistent in recognizing and reinforcing positive behaviors while addressing and correcting undesirable actions. This constancy helps young learners grasp expectations and emphasizes the link between their behaviors and the consequences of those acts. Similarly, when

it comes to using positive reinforcement in a kindergarten context, consistency is essential. Children thrive in predictable situations, and consistent positive reinforcement contributes to an organized and supportive environment (Stanage, 2017). Rumfola (2017) emphasized that as a kindergarten teacher, one must properly explain classroom conduct standards by ensuring that students understand the rules and procedures, and be consistent in reinforcing these expectations. A positive reinforcement plan must also be designed, outlining specific behaviors, reinforcement criteria, and the appropriate prizes or acknowledgements. To guarantee a cohesive approach, this plan can be shared with both students and parents. Application of con-

stant positive reinforcement to all children is also crucial. Consistency aids in the avoidance of ambiguity and creates a fair and equitable learning environment. When offering positive reinforcement, consistent language and tone is important to use. This clarifies expectations for learners and reinforces the positive nature of the feedback. Gwen (2019) conformed that positive reinforcement used consistently adds to a good and supportive learning environment in which students feel secure and motivated to engage in positive activities. Kindergarten teachers may build a consistent and effective positive reinforcement system by setting clear expectations, employing a range of reinforcement strategies, and involve both kids and parents.

3.2.2. Use of Verbal Praise—Another coping mechanism employed by the Kindergarten teachers as they apply positive reinforcement to the kindergartens is, they use verbal praise every time the learners achieve something. According to the participants, they frequently use verbal praise to acknowledge and reinforce positive behaviors of the learners. This includes specific feedback about the behavior exhibited according to the task they accomplished. In a kindergarten setting, verbal praising, as claimed by Mantasiah, Sinring and Aryani (2021), is a powerful and effective method for positive reinforcement. Verbal praise conveys approval and fosters positive conduct by providing in-

stant feedback. This claimed is supported by the study of Salao Espinoza (2022), who suggest that teachers' verbal appreciation can be explicit. Instead of generalizations, give specifics on what the youngster performed well. To show enthusiasm and approbation, a positive and encouraging language can be used that encourages the desired behavior, such as wonderful, excellent, and awesome. Thus, one must remember that positive verbal praise is about reinforcing the process and effort that children put into their tasks as much as the product. Kindergarten teachers can establish a positive and supportive learning environment that stimulates and uplifts young learners by implementing these strategies (Bashir, Ajmal, Rubab, Bhatti, 2020).

3.2.3. Use of Complimenting Gestures—Aside from verbal praises, kindergarten teachers used complimenting gestures as one of the coping mechanisms as they apply positive reinforcement to the learners. According to one of the participants, a simple gesture, such as a high-five, had a significant impact on punctuality. It provided quick positive reinforcement and aided

in the development of a positive teacher-student connection. The finding is congruent to the claim of Samodra and Faridi (2021) that complimentary gestures are an excellent and efficient approach to deliver positive reinforcement to kindergarten learners. Gestures, for example, can improve communication, transmit pleasant feelings, and promote desired behaviors. Rum-

folo (2017) agreed that giving a kindergarten learner a thumbs up to acknowledge and reward positive behavior is an effective reinforcement technique. This modest motion is widely recognized as a statement of approval and encouragement. Also, high-fives can also be used to recognize accomplishments or positive efforts. This is a joyful and encouraging physical display of encouragement for children. Moreover, giving a cheerful wave to learners who demonstrate excellent behaviors is very effective style, such as following orders or actively engaged. Waving conveys a sense of connection and approval (Andrin et al., 2021). The study of Miguel (2020) indicated that the key to effectively using complementing gestures is to make sure they are age-appropriate, culturally sensitive, and considerate of individual preferences. When used consistently and in conjunction with verbal praise, these gestures help to create a good and supportive learning environment in kindergarten.

3.2.4. Enforce Reward System—Reward system, as one of the coping mechanisms of the Kindergarten teachers, is often used to their kindergarten learners. One of the participants shared that the reward system, not only encouraged good behavior, but also taught the students about earning and saving, which are important life skills. This also helps motivate children to consistently exhibit positive actions. The finding is similar to the result of the study of Lynnette, Otaru and Otengah (2021). It found that implementing a reward system in a kindergarten setting can be an effective positive reinforcement method because it offers children with real incentives for showing positive behaviors. However, Tan, Kasivelloo and Abdullah (2022) argued that the usefulness of a reward system as a positive reinforcement approach in kindergarten might vary depending on various aspects, including the system's design, the types of rewards employed, and the children's particular requirements. Sichon and Guhao Jr.

(2020) discovered that teachers should define and clearly specify the exact behaviors they wish to encourage and reinforce. These behaviors should be consistent with the ideals and expectations they have established for their classroom. Stickers, little toys, special privileges, extended playtime, or other objects appealing to the age group might be used as rewards. Viray-Castillejos (2022) maintained that the degree to which a kindergarten reward system is in line with the developmental stage of the learners, the consistency with which it is used, the clarity of expectations, and the classroom culture all play a role in how effective the system is. Teachers can foster an environment that is encouraging and supportive of kindergarten students' social and behavioral development by carefully weighing these variables.

3.2.5. Imposed Individualized Reinforcement—Kindergarten teachers also imposed individualized reinforcement as one of their coping mechanisms. Some of the participants uttered that positive reinforcement has different effects on different children. Some kindergartens are driven by verbal praise, while others prefer material benefits. As Kindergarten teachers, they adjust their reinforcement style to each child's unique requirements and preferences. In a kindergarten context, the study of Sheptunova (2022) had proved that individualized reinforcement is an essential component of positive reinforcement techniques. Positive reinforcement works best when it takes into account each child's individual requirements, preferences, and developmental stage. Conversely, Barton et al., (2018) observed that it is essential for teachers to take time to get to know each child individually, by understanding their strengths, interests, and areas for growth. This knowledge forms the foundation for tailoring positive reinforcement techniques. Moreover, they must recognize that children react to different kinds of positive reinforcement in different ways. While some learners may be driven by

material rewards or exclusive privileges, others may prefer verbal appreciation. Depending on the preferences of each child, one should use different techniques for reinforcement. With this, eachers can establish a constructive and encouraging learning atmosphere that caters to the individual needs of every student by adopting a tailored reinforcement method. The intention is to cultivate in each student a love of learning, motivation, and a sense of belonging (Dobrakowski Łebecka, 2020).

3.2.6. Celebrate Small Success—Showing happiness to any small achievements obtained by the learners is one of the coping mechanisms that the Kindergarten teachers practiced as they apply positive reinforcement to their kindergartens. According to them, they frequently provide opportunity to celebrate accomplishments and milestones, so establishing a pleasant classroom atmosphere. This involves acknowledging a child who has improved in a certain skill or conduct and emphasizing the importance of effort and improvement. learners' accomplishments, no matter how minor, promotes a pleasant learning environment, enhances self-esteem, and reinforces desired behaviors. Children are more likely to stick with their tasks if they receive positive reward for their efforts. Small victories reinforce the value of hard work and foster a growth attitude. The goal is to make the celebration real, timely, and matched with the preferences of the individual child. Small victories not only reinforce great conduct, but they also create a positive and encouraging environment that fosters continuing effort and learning (Stallard, 2019). Mantasiah et al. (2021) even agreed that celebrating small success is a potent positive reinforcement approach that adds to

kindergartners' overall development. It builds their self-esteem, resilience, and enthusiasm for learning, laying the framework for a good and successful educational path.

3.2.7. Employ Reflective Practice—The Kindergarten teachers further employ reflective practice to the class as one of the coping mechanisms. Some of the participants stated that the conduct of regular self-reflection activities among learners assists teachers in assessing the effectiveness of their positive reinforcement tactics, what works well and what can be improved, so that teachers can make informed improvements to their strategies. The idea of Abitova et al. (2020) support the finding as they claimed that reflection activities are critical in kindergarten settings, especially for young learners, as this can provide opportunities to develop important skills and attitudes. Reflection activities for young learners also help them develop critical thinking skills. Children improve their cognitive abilities by learning to observe, question, and evaluate their own experiences. Moreover, Miguel (2020) observed that engaging in reflection activities helps young learners build self-regulation skills. Children learn to appraise events, make decisions, and manage their behavior based on careful thought. This can also aid in the development of a growth mentality in children. They learn that problems are opportunities for growth and learning, which fosters a positive attitude toward effort and perseverance. As a matter of fact, Nafissi and Shafiee (2020) found that reflective activities allow children to reflect on their interactions with peers. Through this, it helps to develop social skills like empathy, cooperation, and conflict resolution.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences and Challenges of Kindergarten Teachers—Presented in Figure 5 is the five (5) educational management insights

drawn from the experiences and challenges of kindergarten teachers. This includes the following: (1) individualization and specification is key, (2) emphasis on intrinsic motivation, (3)

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of Kindergarten Teachers in Applying Positive Reinforcement to Kindergarteners

heighten flexibility and adaptability, (4) establish positive classroom culture, and (5) adopt holistic teaching approach.

3.3.1. Individualization and Specification is Key—The participants learned to individualize and specialize the positive reinforcement that they applied to the learners. According to the participants, they learned that kindergarten teachers must use individualized and specialized positive reinforcement strategies to meet the diverse requirements of their children. The likelihood of success increases when techniques are tailored to each child's preferences and strengths. This finding gets support from the study of Dobrakowski and Lebecka (2020), who revealed that an individualized and specialized approach to reinforcement in kindergartens, focusing on the unique needs and characteristics of individual children, is of paramount importance. This sort of reinforcement strat-

egy considers aspects such as a child's learning style, developmental stage, and any special obstacles or strengths. Likewise, employing an individualized approach to reinforcement in kindergartens is crucial for creating an inclusive, supportive, and effective learning environment. By recognizing and responding to the unique characteristics of each child, teachers tailor support to their specific needs and can contribute to the holistic development and success of every student in their care (Sheptunova, 2022). Morin (2022) further emphasized that this individualized and specialized approach not only improves the learning experience, but also produces a positive and inclusive environment that promotes kindergarten students' general well-being and growth.

3.3.2. Emphasis on Intrinsic Motivation—Aside from rewards which is extrinsic type of motivation, kindergarten teachers learned that the best type of motivation that should be instilled to the minds of the learners is the intrinsic ones. According to them, they must work hard to instill intrinsic motivation in their kindergartens by assisting them in finding delight and satisfaction in their own successes. They also highlighted that they encourage love of learning and pride in personal accomplishments to lessen reliance on external rewards. elatedly, in order to promote a love of learning, independence, and the formation of lifetime learning habits, kindergarten teachers must emphasize intrinsic motivation to the young learners (Smidt Kraft, 2019). Oclaret (2021) maintained that curiosity, a sense of competence, and personal fulfillment

are examples of internal rewards that fuel intrinsic motivation, which originates from within the individual. It can also help to lessen reliance on external rewards. While external reinforcement has its uses, a child's intrinsic motivation may suffer if extrinsic rewards are overused. Emphasizing intrinsic motivation fosters a real interest in learning that can last beyond kindergarten. Intrinsically driven children are more likely to face new difficulties with excitement and interest throughout their educational journey (Ozbeý, Daglıoglu Sarici Bulut, 2023). With this, Barton et al. (2018) concluded that fostering intrinsic motivation in kindergarten lays the groundwork for a lifelong positive approach to learning. It only not makes learning more pleasant for children, but it also provides them with the mentality and abilities necessary for lifelong curiosity, discovery, and personal growth.

3.3.3. Heighten Flexibility and Adaptability—

As kindergarten teachers who build the foundation of the learners, they learned being highly flexible and adaptive according to the diversity of needs of their learners. According to them, they must be flexible and adapt their positive reinforcement styles to the specific requirements of individual learners as well as the overall dynamics of the class. Being willing to test new ways allows teachers to discover what works best for each child. Similar to the result, the finding of Bongabong et al. (2023) maintained that kindergarten teachers must be adaptable and flexible, especially when employing positive reinforcement techniques. These characteristics help teachers to effectively adapt to the different needs, personalities, and dynamics of young learners. Kindergarten learners may have a variety of learning styles. Teachers' adaptability allows them to tailor positive reinforcement strategies to the many ways in which children learn, ensuring that each child receives appropriate support. This is also essential in meeting the needs of various learners. Kindergarten teachers work with young learners who have a wide range of talents, backgrounds, and experiences (Patwardhan, Gordon Mason, 2023).. Hence, Alvarado and Lopez (2020) affirmed that adaptable and flexible attitude contribute to positive reinforcement that is inclusive and supportive of all children. These characteristics enable teachers to manage the dynamic and diverse nature of early childhood education, ensuring that positive reinforcement practices are successful, inclusive, and supportive for all kindergarten students.

3.3.4. Establish Positive Classroom Culture—Another insights that the kindergarten gained is establishing a positive classroom culture. Learners can benefit from rewards to create a sense of teamwork and group responsibility. This can be especially beneficial in encouraging excellent conduct. They also stated that they must develop a sense of community and shared responsibility for maintaining a healthy

learning environment through activities, games, and group discussions. Similarly, Tan et al. (2022) speculated that establishing a positive classroom culture is critical In kindergarten settings because it lays the foundation for a nurturing and successful learning environment. A positive classroom culture adds considerably to kindergarten learners' overall growth, well-being, and success. Additionally, a positive classroom culture fosters an emotionally secure and supportive environment. Kindergarten students who feel safe and appreciated are more likely to express themselves, form meaningful relationships, and feel emotionally well. They can also practice their social skills, learn to communicate, collaborate, and connect positively with their classmates through collaborative activities, group discussions, and shared experiences (Andrin et al., 2021). Sichon and Guhao (2020) implied that establishing a positive classroom culture is critical to kindergarten learners' entire growth and performance. It fosters an environment in which children feel encouraged, interested, and motivated to learn, laying the framework for a positive educational experience that can have long-term consequences for their academic and personal development.

3.3.5. Adopt Holistic Teaching Approach—Another insights that the kindergarten teachers gained based from their experiences and challenges as they applied positive reinforcement to kindergartens is adopting holistic teaching approach. They shared that a holistic teaching method provides learners with the fundamentals required for lifetime learning. It fosters a sense of curiosity, adaptability, and openness to new ideas and problems. The finding is congruent to the claim of Keung and Cheung (2019), who mentioned that adopting a holistic teaching style in kindergarten is critical because it acknowledges the interdependence of numerous areas of a child's development and learning. Holistic education recognizes the social, emotional, physical, and creative compo-

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences and Challenges of Kindergarten Teachers

nents of a child’s development in addition to academic skills. For instance, Aslanian, Bjerkenes and Andresen (2023) thought that learners have many intelligences that extend beyond typical academic evaluations. Holistic education incorporates many intelligences, caters to different learning styles and strengths, and ensures that every kindergarten learner has opportunity to shine. It also fosters critical thinking abilities. Kindergarten students are encouraged to question, evaluate, and investigate, laying the

groundwork for future critical thinking skills. Consequently, in kindergarten, using a holistic teaching method is critical for developing well-rounded individuals who are not just academically proficient but also socially, emotionally, and creatively skilled. It creates the groundwork for a good and inclusive learning experience that contributes to kindergarten students’ life-long development and success (Miguel-Mina, 2018).

4. Implications and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the implications and recommendations of the study after the analysis and interpretation of the findings has been made. The study was conducted to describe the colorful experiences of kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcement to kindergarten learners in Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan, Cotabato during the school year 2023-2024. The study utilized qualitative inquiry, specifically phenomenological design with a total of ten (10) participants selected using purposive non-random sampling design. Using a semi-structured interview guide, the views of the participants regarding their colorful experiences, coping mechanism and educational management insights were extracted. Ethical considerations were undertaken during the conduct of the interview. The audio-recorded interview was transcribed and analyzed using thematic content analysis.

4.1. Findings—Results of the analysis revealed the following: The colorful experiences of the kindergarten teachers in applying techniques in positive reinforcement to kindergartens were diversity of learners’ needs, be-

havioral management, transition periods, and development of core values. The identified coping mechanisms employed by the kindergarten teachers to address the experiences and challenges in applying techniques in positive rein-

forcement to kindergartens were consistency in application, use of verbal praise, use of complimenting gesture, enforce reward system, impose individualized reinforcement, celebrate small success, and employ reflective practice. The educational management insights derived based

from their experiences were individualization and specification is key, emphasis on intrinsic motivation, heighten flexibility and adaptability, establish positive classroom culture, and adopt holistic teaching approach.

4.2. Implications—The colorful experiences of ten (10) selected kindergarten teachers in Arakan West District, Doroluman Arakan Cotabato in applying techniques in positive reinforcement to kindergarten learners is the core of this study. While positive reinforcement techniques can be highly effective in influencing behavior and creating a happy learning environment in kindergarten, teachers also encounter difficulties in implementing them. Kindergarten teachers need to collaborate with their colleagues, seek professional development opportunities, and adjust their positive reinforcement techniques to the specific requirements of their learners and classroom situation. Positive reinforcement in kindergarten requires a careful and adaptable approach that adjusts to the dynamic nature of the learning environment. To mitigate the experiences and challenges they encountered, kindergarten teachers established consistency in application, use verbal praise and complimenting gesture, enforce reward system, impose individualized reinforcement, celebrate

small success, and employ reflective practice. This is crucial for maintaining a positive and effective teaching environment. By employing these coping mechanisms, kindergarten teachers can enhance their effectiveness, resilience, and overall satisfaction in the kindergarten classroom. With this, seeking ongoing professional development opportunities is essential. Training in behavior management, positive reinforcement strategies, and classroom management can help them gain confidence and skills. Educational management insights emphasize that when using positive reinforcement approaches, kindergarten teachers need to take an individualized and specialized approach, taking into account each learner's particular abilities, learning styles, and preferences. It should also include establishing and conveying clear behavioral expectations. Reinforcing positive actions consistently contributes to the creation of a regulated and predictable learning environment. Furthermore, having an enjoyable and supportive environment encourages kindergarten learners to learn and collaborate.

4.3. Future Directions—Based upon the outcomes of the findings and implications, the following recommendations are suggested for consideration: The Department of Education ought to create and communicate clear regulations that encourage the use of positive reinforcement practices in early childhood education. Ensure that policies are consistent with best practices and provide a framework for their implementation across schools. Addi-

tionally, they may create and administer positive reinforcement-focused professional development programs. These programs should give teachers with training, materials, and chances for peer cooperation in order to improve their ability to use positive reinforcement effectively in the classroom. The Schools Division Office may organize in-service trainings that address the specific problems that kindergarten teachers have while using positive reinforcement. These

workshops can provide teachers with hands-on activities, case studies, and practical strategies to help them establish and refine their positive reinforcement practices. The schools may establish mentorship programs that pair experienced kindergarten teachers who are skilled in positive reinforcement approaches with those who are struggling. This mentorship can give continuing support, direction, and a forum for successful strategies to be shared. Teachers may design initiatives that increase parental participation in positive reinforcement strategies. Teachers may provide materials to successfully communicate with parents about the importance of consistency between home and school in encouraging healthy behaviors. The same study can be conducted to investigate the extent of effectiveness of positive reinforcement strategies in diverse kindergarten settings.

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